

Circulating Current Control for Modular Multilevel Converters with (N+1) Selective Harmonic Elimination - PWM

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Abstract—Modular multilevel converters (MMCs) require control of the circulating current, i_{circ} , to improve their operation and efficiency. This is particularly important when low switching frequency modulation techniques, such as selective harmonic elimination (SHE-PWM) are applied. This work provides a novel method to control the circulating current along with (N+1) SHE-PWM. Unlike the case of (2N+1) SHE-PWM, explicit redundant levels are not available and, therefore, different modulation indexes, m_1 and m_2 , are employed in the upper and lower arms to obtain the desired modulation index m_a . Unlike previous (N+1) circulating current methods, the distances between m_a , m_1 and m_2 remain constant to not disturb the phase output voltage, with an interchange of m_1 and m_2 between the arms used to follow the desired i_{circ} . The control adjusts the dc component of the circulating current and the energy stored in the SMs to their references, while maintaining the energy balance between the upper and lower arms. Simulation tests and experimental results, obtained from a single-phase laboratory prototype MMC, validate the proposed control technique.

Index Terms—Selective harmonic elimination (SHE), modular multilevel converter (MMC), optimization algorithms, circulating current.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modular multilevel converters (MMCs) [1], whose scheme is depicted at Fig. 1, are suitable converters to be employed in medium voltage (MV) and high power applications, such as medium voltage direct current (MVDC) networks, MV motor drives and MV wind turbines. Recently, the use of MMC providing virtual inertia for medium voltage grids is also being developed [2]–[6].

Improving the MMC efficiency and dynamic performance are two of the most important challenges for new control strategies and modulation techniques. In MV applications, the efficiency can be improved by utilizing low switching frequency modulations. In particular, when the number of required sub-modules (SMs) of the MMC is not high, selective

Fig. 1. Three-phase MMC with HB SMs.

harmonic elimination - PWM (SHE-PWM) can be used to provide simultaneously low switching losses and elimination of low order harmonics [7], [8]. However, the use of SHE-PWM techniques together with MMC worsen the dynamics of the system, thus hindering the SM capacitor voltage balancing. Consequently, SHE-PWM techniques improve the efficiency but at the expense of requiring higher SM capacitance than carrier-based PWM. In this way, the proposed approach based on SHE-PWM, although general, is well-suited to applications with higher than average energy storage requirements, such as virtual inertia emulation in MV grids [6], [9].

MMCs can operate under two different kinds of SHE-PWM, (2N+1) SHE-PWM [10] or (N+1) SHE-PWM, where N is the number of SMs at each arm and $2N+1$ or $N+1$, respectively, are the number of generated phase output voltage levels. Under the same number of controlled harmonics, (2N+1) SHE-PWM is able to provide lower switching losses and lower total harmonic distortion than (N+1) SHE-PWM. However, (N+1) SHE-PWM is able to provide lower ripple in the circulating current, i_{circ} and lower harmonic content in the DC current, limiting the resonant issues in the DC side of the MMC. Furthermore, (N+1) SHE-PWM provides similar switching

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times in the upper and lower arms, improving the energy balance between both arms. For these reasons, (N+1) SHE-PWM has been selected in the present work for modulating the MMC with reduced switching losses in comparison with high switching frequency modulations such as phase disposition - pulse width modulation (PD-PWM).

In order to improve the dynamic performance when (N+1) SHE-PWM is applied, it is important to provide the MMC with capacity to control the circulating current [11]. Furthermore, the i_{circ} control is required to reduce the MMC losses and the SM capacitor voltage oscillations [12].

However, controlling i_{circ} to operate the MMC with (N+1) SHE-PWM without disturbing the phase output voltage, v_{a0} , is an open issue. The existing i_{circ} controls, which are designed to operate with other modulations such as model predictive control (MPC) or SPWM, have several drawbacks if they are applied along with (N+1) SHE-PWM. Most of these controllers employ different m_a values at each phase arm [12]–[24] or at each SM [16], [25], to track the circulating current reference. However, these techniques would lead to significant disturbances at the low-order harmonic spectrum of the phase output voltage, if they were used with (N+1) SHE-PWM [26]. In addition to these techniques, [27] proposes a dead-beat i_{circ} controller, associated with a model predictive pulse pattern control (MP³C), that provides switching times with opposite correction in the upper and lower arms for a (N+1) modulation. However, in the case of (N+1) SHE-PWM, if these corrections are applied over the set of firing angles that eliminate the lower-order harmonics, significant disturbances would be observed in the phase output voltage. Ref. [28] presented a i_{circ} controller for (2N+1) PWM techniques which utilizes redundant voltage levels to follow the i_{circ} reference. However, this technique is not consistent with (N+1) modulation techniques. Finally, [29] presented a i_{circ} controller which is designed to operate along with (N+1) SHE-PWM. This technique utilises opposite variations in the firing angles for the lower and upper arms. However, such an approach would lead to disturbances in v_{a0} if these variations are significant [30].

This work proposes a novel i_{circ} control which can be applied along with (N+1) SHE-PWM without disturbing the phase output voltage. In particular, like some of the previous (N+1) i_{circ} control methods [12]–[24], different modulation indexes, m_1 and m_2 , in the upper and lower arms are employed to obtain the desired modulation index m_a in the phase output voltage. However, unlike these methods, the values of $(m_a - m_1)$ and $(m_2 - m_a)$ remain constant in time to not disturb the phase output voltage, while the two modulation indexes m_1 and m_2 are interchanged between the arms to follow the desired i_{circ} . All in all, the proposed method has the following features:

- Unlike previous (N+1) SHE-PWM techniques, it is able to balance the upper and lower arm energy at every phase without distorting the phase output voltage, besides maintaining the dc component of i_{circ} and the energy stored at the SMs adjusted to their references. Thereby, this control technique provides limited SM capacitor

voltage ripple when (N+1) SHE-PWM is applied, which also provides low THD and low losses.

- It provides lower ripple in the circulating current, i_{circ} and lower harmonic content in the DC current than (2N+1) SHE-PWM techniques.
- It provides higher efficiency than carrier-based PWM, but it requires bigger capacitors to limit the voltage oscillations. In this way, it represents a good solution in those applications, such as virtual inertia emulation, that already requires high energy storage and where the increase of the efficiency is a bonus.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The proposed i_{circ} control technique is detailed in Section II. Section III reports the simulation results. Section IV analyses the MMC cost associated to the proposed approach. The experimental results are described in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes this paper.

II. PROPOSED METHOD TO CONTROL THE CIRCULATING CURRENT WITH (N+1) SHE-PWM

A. MMC and (N+1) SHE-PWM

(N+1) SHE-PWM provides simultaneous commutations at the upper and lower arms, obtaining the phase output voltage given by (1), where v_{up} is the upper arm voltage and v_{low} is the lower arm voltage (see Fig. 1 and [12] for v_{up} and v_{low} definition) [7], [8]. In this way, unlike (2N+1) SHE-PWM [10], (N+1) SHE-PWM does not provide redundant levels which are useful to control i_{circ} . Therefore, with the aim of controlling i_{circ} , different modulation indexes are utilized in the upper and lower arms and therefore, the commutation instants at both arms are close to each other, but no longer simultaneous. Thereby, the differential voltage given by (2) is no longer zero, providing the ability to control i_{circ} .

$$v_{a0} = \frac{v_{low} + v_{up}}{2}, \quad (1)$$

$$v_{diff} = v_{up} - v_{low}, \quad (2)$$

The sets of firing angles utilized in this work, which provide (N+1) SHE-PWM waveforms with quarter wave (QW) symmetry throughout the m_a range, have been obtained with the calculation method presented in [10], [31]. These sets of angles are stored in look-up tables to be utilized on-line by the MMC controller.

B. Circulating Current Control Principle

The proposed i_{circ} control is able to follow the i_{circ} reference without disturbing the phase output voltage, v_{a0} , when (N+1) SHE-PWM is utilized. The circulating current reference has been obtained according to the algorithm described in [12], [32]. In this way, the i_{circ} contains a dc component which ensures the dc and ac side powers balance. Furthermore, the phase energy is adjusted to its reference and the phase arm energies are completely balanced.

The proposed technique, unlike previous methods [12]–[24], [29], [30], is based on utilizing two different modulation indexes, m_1 and m_2 , whose relationships with m_a , $(m_a - m_1)$

Fig. 2. Definition of modulation indexes for i_{circ} control over a particular continuous set of angles, where $f_{k,i}$ represents the sign of every step (-1 or 1) and $\theta_{k,i}$ is the identifier of every firing angle for a particular modulation index m_i . (a) m_1 and m_2 provide the same switching pattern, fulfilling $f_{k,1} = f_{k,2}, \forall k$. (b) m_1 and m_2 provide different switching patterns but $f_{k,1} = f_{k,2}, \forall k$ is also fulfilled (firing angle rearrangement in m_2).

and $(m_2 - m_a)$, remain constant in time (see Fig. 2 for m_a , m_1 and m_2 definitions). These modulation indexes can be assigned to each arm, depending on the deviation of the circulating current from its reference. Consequently, during part of the fundamental period m_1 can be assigned to the upper arm, i.e. $m_{a,up} = m_1$, and m_2 is assigned to the lower arm $m_{a,low} = m_2$. At a different time interval and depending on the instantaneous value of the circulating current, the assignment of modulation indexes can be interchanged so that $m_{a,up} = m_2$ and $m_{a,low} = m_1$. In this way, the differential voltage can be modulated and the circulating current controlled without distorting the phase output voltage.

When different modulation indexes are utilized at the upper and lower arms, the switching instants are not simultaneous at both arms. This must be considered in the calculation of the Fourier series expansion of v_{a0} . In particular, this expansion, when $(N+1)$ SHE-PWM with QW symmetry is utilized, is given by (3) and (4), where V_{dc} is the dc bus voltage, n is the identifier of every harmonic and b_n is the Fourier series coefficient of every harmonic. As it can be noticed, (3) provides the relationship between m_a , $m_{a,up}$ and $m_{a,low}$.

$$v_{a0} = \sum_{n=1,3,5,7,\dots}^{\infty} b_n \sin(n\omega t) = \frac{v_{low} + v_{up}}{2} = m_a \frac{V_{dc}}{2} = \frac{(m_{a,up} + m_{a,low})V_{dc}}{4}, \quad (3)$$

$$0 \leq m_a \leq 1.27, \quad (4)$$

In addition, v_{a0} depends on v_{up} , given by (5) and v_{low} , given by (6).

$$v_{up} = \sum_{n=1,3,5,7,\dots}^{\infty} b_{n-up} \sin(n\omega t), \quad (5)$$

$$v_{low} = \sum_{n=1,3,5,7,\dots}^{\infty} b_{n-low} \sin(n\omega t), \quad (6)$$

The Fourier series coefficients of v_{up} and v_{low} are given by (7), (8) and (9), (10), respectively, where l is the total number of firing angles in the first QW, V_c is the average SM capacitor

voltage, $\theta_{k,up}$, $\theta_{k,low}$ are the identifiers of every firing angle in the upper and lower arms, respectively and $f_{k,up}$, $f_{k,low}$ are the step sign associated to every firing angle at each arm.

$$b_{n-up} = \frac{4V_c}{n\pi} \sum_{k=1}^l f_{k,up} \cos(n\theta_{k,up}), \quad (7)$$

$$0 \leq \theta_{1,up} < \theta_{2,up} < \dots < \theta_{l,up} \leq \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (8)$$

$$b_{n-low} = \frac{4V_c}{n\pi} \sum_{k=1}^l f_{k,low} \cos(n\theta_{k,low}), \quad (9)$$

$$0 \leq \theta_{1,low} < \theta_{2,low} < \dots < \theta_{l,low} \leq \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (10)$$

In this way, the resulting v_{a0} Fourier series coefficients, b_n , are given by (11) and (12), where N is the number of SMs at each arm (every arm can contain more redundant SMs, for fault tolerant purposes, in such a way that the maximum number of SMs that can be inserted simultaneously is N . In this way, the variable N would remain constant). Eq. (11) provides the dependency of v_{a0} Fourier series expansion on the upper and lower arm commutations.

$$b_n = \frac{b_{n-up} + b_{n-low}}{2} = \frac{2V_c}{n\pi} \sum_{k=1}^l f_{k,up} \cos(n\theta_{k,up}) + f_{k,low} \cos(n\theta_{k,low}), \quad (11)$$

$$V_c = \frac{V_{dc}}{N}, \quad (12)$$

The sign of each term on (11) depends on the specific switching pattern of the voltage waveform and is given by the functions $f_{k,up}$ and $f_{k,low}$ described in (13) and (14). If there is a positive voltage step, $f_k = 1$. Alternatively, if the voltage step is negative, $f_k = -1$.

$$f_{k,up} = \begin{cases} 1 \quad \forall \text{ positive step,} \\ -1 \quad \forall \text{ negative step,} \end{cases}, \quad (13)$$

$$f_{k,low} = \begin{cases} 1 \quad \forall \text{ positive step,} \\ -1 \quad \forall \text{ negative step,} \end{cases}, \quad (14)$$

Eq. (11) provides the value of every harmonic of v_{a0} . Therefore, the equation system which must be solved to control the fundamental and lower-order harmonics, is given by (15). This system of equations does not increase the switching frequency with respect to the original $(N+1)$ SHE-PWM system of equations that provides simultaneous commutations at both arms [7], [8].

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{2}{\pi N} (f_{1,up} \cos(\theta_{1,up}) + f_{1,low} \cos(\theta_{1,low}) + \dots \\ & + f_{l,up} \cos(\theta_{l,up}) + f_{l,low} \cos(\theta_{l,low})) - \frac{m_{a,up} + m_{a,low}}{4} = 0, \\ & \frac{2}{5\pi N} (f_{1,up} \cos(5\theta_{1,up}) + f_{1,low} \cos(5\theta_{1,low}) + \dots \\ & + f_{l,up} \cos(5\theta_{l,up}) + f_{l,low} \cos(5\theta_{l,low})) = 0, \\ & \vdots \\ & \frac{2}{n\pi N} (f_{1,up} \cos(n\theta_{1,up}) + f_{1,low} \cos(n\theta_{1,low}) + \dots \\ & + f_{l,up} \cos(n\theta_{l,up}) + f_{l,low} \cos(n\theta_{l,low})) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

In general, the utilized sets of angles $\theta_{k,up}$ and $\theta_{k,low}$, $k = 1 \dots l$, must be executed completely over the fundamental

Fig. 3. (a) Relationship between v_{diff} and v_{a0} according to the order of firing angles at the upper and lower arms. (b) Criterion to define the sign of v_{diff} .

period to avoid distorting the fundamental and the lower-order harmonic spectrum of v_{a0} . This constraint can be fulfilled by setting m_a , $m_{a,up}$ and $m_{a,low}$ constant within a period. In this way, $m_{a,up} = m_1$ and $m_{a,low} = m_2$ (and consequently, $\theta_{k,up} = \theta_{k,1}$ and $\theta_{k,low} = \theta_{k,2}, \forall k$) where $(m_a - m_1)$ and $(m_2 - m_a)$ remain constant over the whole fundamental period. In addition, if the step sign associated with every firing angle is the same for m_1 and m_2 ($f_{k,1} = f_{k,2}, \forall k$) (see Fig. 2-(a)), the switching angles assigned to the upper arm can be interchanged with those assigned to the lower arm and vice versa, without distorting the output voltage. This is demonstrated using (15) where regardless of $\theta_{k,up} = \theta_{k,1}$ and $\theta_{k,low} = \theta_{k,2}$ or $\theta_{k,up} = \theta_{k,2}$ and $\theta_{k,low} = \theta_{k,1}$, the value given by (15) remains constant. In other words, the modulation indexes, m_1 and m_2 , can be interchanged between the upper and lower arms at every switching instant. The constraint of $f_{k,1} = f_{k,2}, \forall k$ is fulfilled in continuous sets of firing angles when m_1 and m_2 provide the same switching pattern (see Fig. 2-(a)) or when the number of firing angles associated with positive and negative steps is the same for m_1 and m_2 and the firing angle identifiers are defined as shown in Fig. 2-(b).

This degree of freedom, as can be noticed at Fig. 3-(a), allows to insert a positive or negative v_{diff} , depending on the specific assignment of the switching angles, thus allowing the regulation of i_{circ} . Consequently, a i_{circ} reference can be tracked, determining the sign of v_{diff} according to the relationship between the i_{circ} real and reference values (see Fig. 3-(b)) and applying the corresponding switching angles to have the desired v_{diff} .

Fig. 4. Assignment of the next firing angles to the upper and lower arms, depending on the sign of v_{diff} .

C. Implementation of the Control Algorithm: Assignment of Firing Angles

1) *Definition of m_1 and m_2* : Once the required m_a is determined, m_1 and m_2 must be defined. With the aim of obtaining a low i_{circ} ripple, whose value is given by (16), where L is the arm inductance and f is the fundamental frequency, m_1 and m_2 must be close to m_a and the set of firing angles must be continuous. Fig. 2 shows a particular continuous set of angles, where m_1 and m_2 are defined according to m_a .

$$|\Delta i_{circ}| = \frac{V_c}{4L\pi f} |\theta_{k,up} - \theta_{k,low}|, \quad (16)$$

The relationship between m_1 , m_2 and m_a is determined to achieve a trade off between the steady state i_{circ} ripple and the control response under transient operating conditions. This relationship will be obtained empirically and therefore, a complete study must be implemented under different operating conditions. Section III shows an example of this study.

2) *Control Technique for Separate Firing Angles*: Once m_1 and m_2 have been defined, the algorithm depicted in the flowchart of Fig. 4 must be followed to assign the switching angles to the upper and lower arms. Depending on the instantaneous phase ωt and the utilized set of firing angles, the next pair of switching instants, $\theta_{k,1}$ and $\theta_{k,2}$, besides their corresponding step sign, f_k , are identified. In addition to that, the required sign of v_{diff} is determined comparing the reference and actual values of the circulating current. Afterwards, depending on f_k , the order of $\theta_{k,1}$ and $\theta_{k,2}$ and

Fig. 5. Example of operation of the proposed circulating current control. Cases c, a and h, according to Fig. 4 are executed to follow the i_{circ} reference. Set of angles, v_{diff} and v_{a0} are shown.

the required sign of v_{diff} , the switching instants are assigned to the upper and lower arms, providing $\theta_{k,up} = \theta_{k,1}$ and $\theta_{k,low} = \theta_{k,2}$ or $\theta_{k,up} = \theta_{k,2}$ and $\theta_{k,low} = \theta_{k,1}$, according to the scheme depicted at Fig. 4. An example of the i_{circ} control operation is depicted at Fig. 5. This figure shows the cases "c", "a" and "h", represented in Fig. 4. For instance, for the first pair of firing angles ($k = 1$), where the actual value of i_{circ} is lower than the reference value and consequently, the required $v_{diff} > 0$, $f_1 = 1$ and the set of firing angles is such that $\theta_{1,1} > \theta_{1,2}$ (see Fig. 5 for case "c"), the required assignment of firing angles according to Fig. 4 is such that $\theta_{1,up} = \theta_{1,2}$ and $\theta_{1,low} = \theta_{1,1}$. This assignment, according to (2), generates a positive v_{diff} that produces an increase, given by (16), in the circulating current as depicted in Fig. 5. Similar reasoning can be applied for any other condition.

The proposed control method processes every pair of firing angles, $\theta_{k,1}$ and $\theta_{k,2}$, independently from the rest of pairs of firing angles. However, there is an exception when two or even more pairs of firing angles are close to each other and the upper/lower voltage limits at every arm may be exceeded. This is described below.

3) *Control Technique for Close Firing Angles:* When two consecutive pairs of firing angles are very close to each other, $\theta_{k,1}$ or $\theta_{k,2}$ could be fired later than $\theta_{k+1,1}$ or $\theta_{k+1,2}$ (Fig. 6). This occasion will be correctly addressed by the scheme depicted at Fig. 4 because every pair of firing angles ($\theta_{k,1}$ and $\theta_{k,2}$) will be managed independently from another close pair of angles ($\theta_{k+1,1}$ and $\theta_{k+1,2}$) and therefore, $\theta_{k,1}$, $\theta_{k,2}$, $\theta_{k+1,1}$ and $\theta_{k+1,2}$ will be fired according to the required v_{diff} at the firing instant.

However, the algorithm displayed in Fig. 4 only takes into account the value of i_{circ} to assign the firing angles (criterion 1). If, at some switching points, the assignment of angles obtained with the algorithm of Fig. 4 makes v_{up} or v_{low} exceed their maximum/minimum achievable voltage limits, this assignment is disregarded and the opposite assignment is used (criterion 2). In particular, if the sign of v_{diff} requires for instance that $\theta_{k+1,up} = \theta_{k+1,1}$ and $\theta_{k+1,low} = \theta_{k+1,2}$, but

Fig. 6. Example of pairs of firing angles which are close to each other. There is only overlap of two pairs of angles.

Criterion ① : Following i_{circ} reference (Fig.4)

Criterion ② : No exceeding V_{upper} or V_{lower} limits

Fig. 7. Case of close firing angles (overlap of 2 pairs of firing angles) with limitation of maximum arm voltage overtaking. v_{diff} , v_{a0} , v_{up} and v_{low} are shown.

the maximum/minimum voltage limits are exceeded, the final assignment will be $\theta_{k+1,up} = \theta_{k+1,2}$ and $\theta_{k+1,low} = \theta_{k+1,1}$ (see Fig. 7). In this way, this pair of firing angles will not provide a correct sign for v_{diff} to regulate the i_{circ} , but the voltage limits are not exceeded and the output voltage is not distorted. In particular, Fig. 7 shows a case where a positive v_{diff} is required to follow the i_{circ} reference but at some switching instants criterion 2 is applied and negative v_{diff} is provided. However, this only happens when the output voltage is close to its maximum/minimum level and therefore, the rest of firing angles over the fundamental period will allow the control to follow the i_{circ} reference (criterion 1). This issue will be shown at the simulation results. Similar reasoning is followed when three or even more pairs of firing angles are located very close to each other.

Finally, crossings between firing angles over the m_a range can also be noticed at Fig. 2. These cases are particular examples of close firing angles and they will be processed in the same way.

D. Upper and Lower Arm Voltage Generation

The complete procedure to generate the upper and lower arm voltages is described in the scheme depicted in Fig. 8. The algorithm shown in Fig. 4 is inserted in the block dedicated to the assignment of the next pair of firing angles to the upper and lower arms. Once these firing angles have been assigned, the

Fig. 8. Upper and lower arm voltage generation.

upper and lower arm voltages are calculated according to m_a , ωt , the phase angle value, α , and the sets of angles (loaded in look-up tables). In addition, it is required to select which SMs are inserted or bypassed to balance the SM capacitor voltages. For this purpose, the balancing algorithm of [7], [8] is applied. It operates solely in case there is a change in the phase output voltage. In this way, the switching losses are not increased due to the balancing algorithm.

Finally, it is important to remark that the proposed algorithm displayed in Fig. 8 does not provide any means to compensate the effect of the SM capacitor voltage ripple on the generated arm voltage by adjusting the values of the modulation index, as it is done by other conventional i_{circ} compensated control methods applied along with high switching frequency carrier based PWM modulations. In case of (N+1) SHE-PWM, such a compensation method does not work since it would imply to modify significantly the firing angles, breaking the waveform symmetry and distorting the phase output voltage spectrum. Nevertheless, as it will be shown at Section III-C, the effect of the SM capacitor voltage ripple on the phase output voltage is very limited and can be compensated by an external controller. On the other hand, due to the lack of compensation in $m_{a,up}$ and $m_{a,low}$, the SM capacitor voltage ripple will affect the i_{circ} ripple, in particular, its second harmonic. However, due to the proposed i_{circ} control, this effect will also be limited, as it will be shown in section III-B.

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
# of SMs per arm, N	10
dc link Voltage, V_{dc}	22500V
SM capacitor, C	3.2mF
SM capacitor voltage, V_c	2250V
Nominal phase output current - RMS, I_a	318A
Arm inductor, L	18mH (0.1 p.u.) [33], [34]
Load, R_L and L_L . Star configuration.	24 Ω and 8mH
# of Angles (1 st QW) (N+1) SHE-PWM	17
Fundamental frequency, f	50Hz
First non-eliminated harmonic	53 rd
Modulation index, m_a	0.2 and 0.9
PI control for DC-link voltage	$P=2.5e^{-9}$, $I=9e^{-8}$
Arm energy balance control, K	$1e^{-5}$

TABLE II
 i_{circ} RIPPLE - RMS (A) DEPENDING ON m_a AND $\Delta m_a = (m_2 - m_1)/2$

m_a	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1
$\Delta m_a = 0.005$	0.60	1.15	1.25	3.20	2.61	3.80	6.14	4.71	9.10	18.48
$\Delta m_a = 0.01$	1.05	2.53	3.72	2.26	5.57	6.19	10.05	4.11	4.24	7.69
$\Delta m_a = 0.015$	1.61	3.71	5.89	2.77	6.95	10.04	7.89	4.64	4.88	9.17
$\Delta m_a = 0.02$	2.17	6.18	7.05	4.57	11.97	6.53	8.97	5.92	7.97	11.21

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The proposed i_{circ} control has been validated utilizing a Matlab/Simulink model which contains a three-phase MMC, whose scheme is depicted at Fig. 1. In particular, the MMC contains 10 SMs at every arm and the (N+1) SHE-PWM waveforms have been calculated using 17 firing angles in the first QW (see Table I). Simulation studies are used to provide an insight into the selection process of Δm_a and the sizing of the SM capacitance. In addition, the validation of the proposed algorithm, together with the analysis of the impact of the SM capacitor voltage ripple on the generated output voltage and the evaluation of the efficiency and THD are also disclosed.

A. Δm_a Selection and SM Capacitance Design

1) Δm_a Selection: The selection of the most suitable Δm_a for each operating condition is based on an empirical approach where multiple simulations are performed to calculate Δm_a . The optimal Δm_a is selected to minimize the i_{circ} ripple for every m_a and power factor. Table II provides the i_{circ} ripple obtained from different $\Delta m_a = m_2 - m_1$ values, throughout the m_a range. The i_{circ} ripple depends on the m_a value because of two reasons. Firstly, different switching patterns provide different Δi_{circ} and secondly, the second harmonic energy variation at every arm increases when m_a and i_a are increased. With the help of the results disclosed in Table II the following conclusions can be drawn:

- If Δm_a is too small, the i_{circ} is not able to follow its reference correctly during transients as the i_{circ} controller becomes too slow. In addition, in steady state conditions, a small Δm_a might be insufficient to compensate the effect of the SM capacitor voltage ripple on i_{circ} . Consequently, in those operating conditions where the voltage ripple is high, the steady state i_{circ} ripple will also be high. This can be appreciated in Table II, when

Fig. 9. (N+1) SHE-PWM waveforms with 17 angles in the first QW, f equal to 50Hz and m_a from 0.2 to 0.9. (a) Reference (red) and actual (blue) circulating current when $\Delta m_a = 0.01$ for $m_a = 0.2$ and $\Delta m_a = 0.02$ for $m_a = 0.9$. (b) Reference (red) and actual (blue) circulating current when $\Delta m_a = 0.005$ for $m_a = 0.2$ and $\Delta m_a = 0.01$ for $m_a = 0.9$.

$m_a = 0.9$. Under this specific working condition, the second harmonic of the voltage ripple is relatively high and $\Delta m_a = 0.005$ is insufficient to provide a smooth i_{circ} . Consequently, a higher i_{circ} ripple than with larger Δm_a values is generated.

- Alternatively, if Δm_a is too high, the i_{circ} ripple increases unnecessarily (for instance, in case of $m_a = 0.9$, $\Delta m_a = 0.02$ is too high). In this case, the control will be faster but at the expense of high i_{circ} ripple.
- For the specific case study analyzed in this paper, Δm_a must be ≥ 0.005 to operate correctly under transient states and ≤ 0.02 to provide low i_{circ} ripple. Out of all the Δm_a values shown in Table II, the Δm_a selected for a particular m_a is the value that provides lower steady state i_{circ} ripple. In this way, a trade-off between i_{circ} ripple and control response to transients is achieved.

Two examples of how Δm_a affects the i_{circ} control operation can be noticed at Fig. 9, where a transition from $m_a = 0.2$ to $m_a = 0.9$ is shown. In Fig. 9-(a), $\Delta m_a = 0.01$ for $m_a = 0.2$ and $\Delta m_a = 0.02$ for $m_a = 0.9$. On the other hand, in Fig. 9-(b) $\Delta m_a = 0.005$ for $m_a = 0.2$ and $\Delta m_a = 0.01$ for $m_a = 0.9$. The first configuration provides a faster control (the i_{circ} maximum value in the transient is lower) but a higher i_{circ} steady state ripple. In this way, as the second configuration is also able to follow correctly the i_{circ} reference under transient operating conditions but with lower i_{circ} ripple, this configuration has been selected.

Finally, in case the MMC operates under different power factors, Δm_a must not only be determined for each m_a , but also for every power factor, employing a similar empirical approach. This process has been implemented to obtain the efficiency study of Section III-D.

2) *SM Capacitance Design*: The design of the SM capacitance has been based on [12] that shows the dependency of the SM capacitor voltage ripple on the m_a and the current phase angle values. According to [12], the minimum required SM capacitance to maintain the voltage ripple of the SM within $\pm 10\%$ should be $C = 1.6mF$ (32kJ/MVA) for the case study analyzed in this paper. Ref. [12] provides this value assuming that i_{circ} is fully controlled and that the energy is distributed evenly among all the arm capacitors instantaneously. Nevertheless, in case of (N+1) SHE-PWM, due to its low switching frequency and the limitations in the v_{diff}

Fig. 10. (N+1) SHE-PWM waveforms. Until $t = 2.015s$ the i_{circ} is not controlled. At $t = 2.015s$ the proposed controller is applied. The results have been obtained with 17 angles in the first QW, $f = 50Hz$ and $m_a = 0.9$. (a) Reference (red) and actual (blue) circulating current. (b) Differential voltage. (c) V_{ab} waveform. (d) V_{ab} spectrum.

values, $C = 1.6mF$ provides a SM capacitor voltage ripple higher than 10%. The required SM capacitance to maintain the SM capacitor voltage ripple lower than 10% for any operating condition (any modulation index and current phase angle) is $C = 3.2mF$ (64kJ/MVA) when the proposed (N+1) SHE-PWM is used. This is an important drawback of SHE-PWM with regard to carrier-based PWM. In any case, it is important to remark that this drawback is not attributable to the i_{circ} control scheme proposed, but it is a general limitation of SHE-PWM techniques. In fact, as it will be shown in Section III-E the proposed i_{circ} control technique reduces considerably the SM voltage ripple. If no i_{circ} control technique is used, the required SM capacitance to limit the voltage ripple should be even higher when SHE-PWM is used.

These considerations make the proposed i_{circ} control technique along with (N+1) SHE-PWM recommendable for applications which already need high stored energy capacity such as inertia emulation [6], [9] and where the improvement of the efficiency achievable with SHE-PWM techniques is a bonus.

B. Waveform Assessment

The operation of the proposed i_{circ} control can be observed at Fig. 10. In particular, i_{circ} is uncontrolled until $t = 2.015s$. During this period of time, the i_{circ} ripple, which contains a fundamental harmonic and a 2nd harmonic, is significant as shown in Fig. 10-(a). The fundamental harmonic is given by the energy unbalance between the upper and lower arms at every phase. The high 2nd harmonic is due to the uncontrolled stored energy in the SMs at every phase. After $t = 2.015s$, the proposed i_{circ} controller is enabled. As a result, the i_{circ} reference is followed correctly, eliminating the fundamental component and reducing significantly the 2nd harmonic component of the i_{circ} ripple (see Fig. 10-(a)). The reference can be followed through the utilization of positive and negative narrow pulses in v_{diff} (due to the employment of two different modulation indexes, m_1 and m_2) (see Fig. 10-(b)). These pulses are not present when i_{circ} control is not

Fig. 11. (N+1) SHE-PWM waveforms with 17 angles in the first QW, f equal to 50Hz and $m_a = 1.01$, where there are instants which provide an opposite i_{circ} increase to avoid exceeding the upper and lower output voltage limits. Despite this fact, the control is able to follow the i_{circ} reference. (a) V_{an} waveform in detail. (b) Reference (red) and actual (blue) circulating current in detail.

applied. Finally, the line-line voltage v_{ab} and its spectrum are shown at Figs. 10-(c) and 10-(d), respectively. The first non-eliminated harmonic is the 53^{rd} , as expected when 17 firing angles are used, confirming that the proposed i_{circ} control does not disturb the phase output voltage.

In case there are close firing angles which provide a phase output voltage that may exceed the maximum or minimum allowed levels by the converter, v_{diff} will have an opposite sign to the desired one. In this way, the i_{circ} will vary in the opposite direction. This case is highlighted by the green arrows in Fig. 11. In addition to that, there are other periods of time (indicated by red arrows in Fig. 11-(b)) where the evolution of the circulating current is also opposite to the desired one. This is due to the 2^{nd} harmonic component of the i_{circ} ripple and the lack of firing angles during these periods of time. However, these instances do not prevent the control from following the DC and fundamental components of the i_{circ} reference.

Fig. 12 shows the operation of the converter when the modulation index is changed from $m_a = 0.2$ to $m_a = 0.9$ at $t = 0.5$ s. In particular, Fig. 12-(a) shows the line-line V_{AB} voltage. The phase currents are depicted at Fig. 12-(b) and the upper and lower arm currents of phase A are shown in Fig. 12-(c). As it can be noticed, the currents are balanced. Fig. 12-(d), which contains the i_{circ} and its corresponding reference, shows how the control is able to follow the i_{circ} reference under transient states. The upper and lower SM capacitor voltages are depicted at Figs. 12-(e) and 12-(f). Both figures show an increment in the SM capacitor voltage ripple when the output power is increased. However, despite the transients, all the SM capacitor voltages are balanced and the SM capacitor voltage ripple is always lower than 5%. On the other hand, Figs. 12-(g) and 12-(h) show the V_{AB} spectrum. As expected, when 17 firing angles are used in combination with the (N+1) SHE-PWM, the first undesired harmonic is located at 2650 Hz (53^{rd}). These results further demonstrate that the proposed i_{circ} control does not disturb the phase output voltage.

C. Study of the Impact of SM Capacitor Voltage Ripple on Phase Output Voltage

Carrier-based PWM modulations allow the implementation of algorithms that compensate the SM capacitor voltage vari-

Fig. 12. (N+1) SHE-PWM waveforms with 17 angles in the first QW, f equal to 50Hz and a transition of the m_a value from 0.2 to 0.9 at $t = 0.5$ s. (a) V_{AB} waveform. (b) Phase currents. (c) Upper and lower arm currents of phase A. (d) Reference (red) and actual (blue) circulating current. (e) Upper SM capacitor voltages. (f) Lower SM capacitor voltages. (g) V_{AB} spectrum for $m_a = 0.2$. (h) V_{AB} spectrum for $m_a = 0.9$.

ations to provide exactly the desired arm voltages [13].

However, if a compensated mode is used along with SHE-PWM (regardless of whether the proposed circulating current control is used or not), those variations in $m_{a,up}$ and $m_{a,low}$ throughout the fundamental cycle provide modifications in the firing angles and therefore, the phase output voltage can be distorted significantly. Due to this reason, the compensated operation mode has not been considered for SHE-PWM.

Nevertheless, according to (11) and (12) and assuming a SM capacitor voltage ripple of 10%, the maximum variation in the phase output voltage will also be a 10% of the ideal value given by the sets of angles. In this way, the eliminated harmonics will experience a maximum of 10% variation in their amplitude with respect to the ideal amplitude, which is close to zero, and therefore, the final amplitude will still be very low. On the other hand, the fundamental harmonic amplitude could undergo a variation of 10% of its ideal value, that in this case is significant, but this error can be compensated by the external controller. In addition, due to the fact that the SM capacitor voltage ripple is not always 10% throughout the fundamental cycle, the resulting distortion will be lower than 10%.

Fig. 13 provides the resulting phase output voltage spectrum

Fig. 13. (a) Line-line output voltage spectrum with ideal DC sources. (b) Zoom of Line-line output voltage spectrum with ideal DC sources. (c) Line-line output voltage spectrum with real capacitors. (d) Zoom of Line-line output voltage spectrum with real capacitors.

provided directly by the arm voltages in case of SMs with ideal DC sources or real capacitors (3.2mF). As it can be noticed at Figs. 13-(b) and 13-(d), under real operating conditions, the amplitude of eliminated harmonics is higher than under ideal conditions, but those amplitudes are still very low (lower than 0.005 p.u.). On the other hand, the fundamental harmonic amplitude varies by 0.6% (from 0.9 p.u. to 0.906 p.u (see Figs. 13-(a) and 13-(c))) that can be compensated by the external controller.

D. Efficiency Study

An efficiency study (see Fig. 14) is presented to benchmark the losses and THD provided by the MMC when (N+1) SHE-PWM is used against those provided by phase disposition - pulse with modulation (PD-PWM). As it will be described below, the switching losses will be significantly different in case of (N+1) SHE-PWM and PD-PWM due to the difference in the switching frequency between the two modulations. In particular, the switching frequency of (N+1) SHE-PWM is given by (17), where f and l are the fundamental frequency and the number of firing angles in the first QW, respectively. On the other hand, the switching frequency of PD-PWM is given by (18), where f_c and n_t are the carrier frequency and the number of transitions between carriers over half fundamental period. The value of n_t will increase in case m_a increases, providing higher switching losses.

$$f_{sw-(N+1)SHE} = 2lf, \quad (17)$$

$$f_{sw-PDPWM} \approx f_c + n_t f, \quad (18)$$

The study has been conducted with the simulation parameters of Table I. Therefore, $f_{sw-(N+1)SHE} = 1700\text{Hz}$. In addition, as it can be noticed, the first non eliminated harmonic in case of (N+1) SHE-PWM is 2650Hz when 17 firing angles are used in the first QW. In this way, with the aim of comparing the losses, the first band of harmonics provided by PD-PWM will be centred in 2650Hz, utilizing $f_c = 2650\text{Hz}$ (for instance, in case of $m_a = 0.9$, $f_{sw-PDPWM} = 3100\text{Hz}$).

Fig. 14. (a) Comparison of conduction losses: (N+1) SHE-PWM / PD-PWM. (b) Switching losses comparison: (N+1) SHE-PWM / PD-PWM. (c) Total losses comparison: (N+1) SHE-PWM / PD-PWM. (d) THD comparison between (N+1) SHE-PWM and PD-PWM for a three-phase load of 24Ω & 8mH.

The calculation of conduction and switching losses at a CM600HB-90H Powerex IGBT is based on the method published by [35], [36]. In particular, a junction temperature $T_j = 125^\circ\text{C}$ and a current factor $k = 1$ are used to simplify the calculations [16]. The simulation results, obtained with nominal phase current (see Table I), are provided as a function of both the power factor and m_a .

Fig. 14-(a) shows the ratio between the (N+1) SHE-PWM

Fig. 15. (a) Arm currents when PD-PWM is utilized. (b) i_{circ} when PD-PWM is utilized. (c) Upper arm SM capacitor voltages when PD-PWM is utilized. (d) Lower arm SM capacitor voltages when PD-PWM is utilized. (e) Arm currents when (N+1) SHE-PWM with the proposed control is utilized. (f) i_{circ} when (N+1) SHE-PWM with the proposed control is utilized. (g) Upper arm SM capacitor voltages when (N+1) SHE-PWM with the proposed control is utilized. (h) Lower arm SM capacitor voltages when (N+1) SHE-PWM with the proposed control is utilized. (i) Arm currents when (N+1) SHE-PWM without i_{circ} control is utilized. (j) i_{circ} when (N+1) SHE-PWM without i_{circ} control is utilized. (k) Upper arm SM capacitor voltages when (N+1) SHE-PWM without i_{circ} control is utilized. (l) Lower arm SM capacitor voltages when (N+1) SHE-PWM without i_{circ} control is utilized.

and PD-PWM conduction losses. The surface is always close to one, meaning that the conduction losses of both modulation techniques are similar (maximum difference of 4%). The variations in the surface throughout the current phase angle range is due to variations in the i_{circ} ripple provided by (N+1) SHE-PWM (see Section II-D). On the other hand, the switching losses under (N+1) SHE-PWM are significantly lower than the ones under PD-PWM, (Fig. 14-(b)). This improvement is particularly noticeable for higher m_a values, where the switching frequency of PD-PWM is higher.

Regarding the total losses (see Fig. 14-(c)), (N+1) SHE-PWM is more efficient than PD-PWM throughout the m_a and phase current ranges. Finally, Fig. 14-(d) shows the THD of voltage waveforms. It can be observed that both modulations exhibit similar THD. However, it is convenient to highlight that the (N+1) SHE-PWM modulation is able to achieve these THD values with significantly lower losses.

E. Comparison of Conventional and Proposed Control Methods

The operation of the MMC has been studied when different i_{circ} control techniques are applied with (N+1) modulations. In particular, the following cases have been compared between each other (see Fig. 15): i) conventional i_{circ} control which operates along with PD-PWM [12], [13] and where a resonant controller is added to reject completely the second harmonic in i_{circ} , ii) the proposed i_{circ} control along with (N+1) SHE-PWM and iii) (N+1) SHE-PWM without i_{circ} control.

A transient state has been simulated for every case where the m_a changes from 0.2 to 0.9. In particular, the transient happens at $t = 0.3s$ in case of PD-PWM and at $t = 0.2s$ in case of (N+1) SHE-PWM with and without control.

As it can be noticed at Fig. 15, the SM capacitor voltage ripple and the i_{circ} ripple provided by PD-PWM are lower than the ripples provided by (N+1) SHE-PWM with the proposed i_{circ} control. However, (N+1) SHE-PWM provides lower switching losses (see Fig. 14-(b)) and in addition, the i_{circ} ripple and the SM capacitor voltage ripple are still limited. In particular, the SM capacitor voltage ripple is under 10% and regarding the nominal arm current, the i_{circ} ripple is also lower than 10%.

On the other hand, if the (N+1) SHE-PWM is operated without circulating current control, both the i_{circ} and the SM capacitor voltage ripples increase significantly, the transitory state is much longer and under particular operating conditions, the MMC could become uncontrolled.

IV. MMC COST ANALYSIS

As it has been commented in Section III-A2, the proposed approach along with (N+1) SHE-PWM requires approximately twice as much SM capacitance as other i_{circ} controls based on high switching frequency modulations, such as PD-PWM, in case of applications with standard storage requirements. This implies a significant increase in the MMC cost. Otherwise, in case of applications with higher than average energy storage, this increase is not relevant. With the aim of estimating this increment, the cost of the MMC detailed in Table I has been estimated for two different MV applications, i) medium voltage STATCOM and ii) virtual inertia emulation. Both applications will provide the same apparent power, 7.6MVA and only the energy storage will be different between each other. An energy storage of 37.2kJ/MVA [37] and 70.4kJ/MVA [6] have been taken as a reference for the medium voltage STATCOM and the virtual inertia emulation,

TABLE III
COST ESTIMATION (P.U.) OF MMC COMPONENTS FOR DIFFERENT APPLICATIONS AND MODULATIONS

	Silicon	Capacitors	Filter	Total Cost
STATCOM PD-PWM	0.3	0.328	0.075	0.703
STATCOM (N+1) SHE-PWM	0.3	0.565	0.075	0.94
Virtual Inertia PD-PWM	0.3	0.625	0.075	1
Virtual Inertia (N+1) SHE-PWM	0.3	0.625	0.075	1

TABLE IV
EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Parameter	Value
# of SMs per arm, N	4
dc link Voltage, V_{dc}	200V
SM capacitor, C	3.6mF
SM capacitor voltage, V_C	50V
Arm inductor, L	3.6mH
Initial Load, R_L and L_L	22 Ω and 4mH
Final Load, R_L and L_L	11 Ω and 4mH
Nominal phase current - RMS	5A
# of Angles, per QW, for (N+1) SHE	17
Fundamental frequency, f	50Hz
First non-eliminated non-triple harmonic	53 rd
Modulation index, m_a	0.85
PI control for dc-link voltage	$P=0.0015, I=0.009$
Arm energy balance control, K	0.05

respectively, when a high switching frequency modulation is utilized. In case of (N+1) SHE-PWM, according to the conclusions of Section III-A2, the energy storage designed for the medium voltage STATCOM is 64kJ/MVA. Instead, for the virtual inertia emulation, increasing the energy storage beyond 70.4kJ/MVA is not required when (N+1) SHE-PWM is used.

The cost of the different components of the converter, considering the capacitors, silicon and filter, has been estimated regarding [38], [39] and data provided from component manufacturers. In Table III the cost is represented in p.u. to compare the results. The values are normalized with respect to the most expensive case that is the virtual inertia emulation. As it can be noticed, in case of STATCOMs, utilizing (N+1) SHE-PWM implies a significant increase of the converter cost, due to the higher energy storage, with respect to PD-PWM. This issue limits the practical use of the proposed approach in STATCOM applications. However, in case of virtual inertia emulation, both modulation techniques require the same energy storage and therefore, the converter cost is the same. As a result, in applications such as virtual inertia emulation, the proposed approach is interesting to improve the efficiency of the MMC, providing similar THD and cost.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The proposed circulating current control technique has been experimentally validated on a single-phase MMC which is shown in [10]. The experimental set-up features are included at Table IV, providing $f_{sw-(N+1)SHE} = 1700\text{Hz}$. 17 firing angles have been utilized in the first QW along with the proposed i_{circ} control technique.

Fig. 16-(a) and 16-(b) show the phase neutral voltage for $m_a = 0.85$ and its corresponding spectrum, respectively. As

Fig. 16. Experimental results for (N+1) SHE-PWM with 17 angles in the first QW, $f = 50\text{Hz}$ and $m_a = 0.85$. (a) V_a waveform. (b) V_a spectrum. (c) Output phase current. (d) Upper and lower arm currents. (e) Upper SM capacitor voltages. (f) Lower SM capacitor voltages. (g) Circulating current.

it can be noticed, the first non-triplen and non-eliminated harmonic is located at 2650Hz (53rd harmonic), as it is expected when 17 firing angles are used, corroborating that the proposed i_{circ} control does not disturb the phase neutral voltage. Nevertheless, Fig. 16-(b) also exhibits low frequency triplen harmonics. This is due to the fact that the firing angles have been calculated for a three-phase system, but the experimental platform comprises a single-phase MMC. Consequently, the triplen harmonics are not naturally cancelled. On the other hand, Fig. 16-(c) shows the phase current where a load step from 22 Ω and 4mH to 11 Ω and 4mH at $t = 0.45\text{s}$ is applied. The arm currents are depicted in Fig. 16-(d), where the load step can also be noticed. The increment in the phase current provides an increment in the SM capacitor voltage ripple as it is shown in Figs. 16-(e) and 16-(f). However, despite this increment, all the SM capacitor voltages are balanced, the SM capacitor voltage ripple is always lower than 5% and the SM capacitor averaged voltage is adjusted to its reference. In addition, these figures show how the energies stored in the upper and lower arms are correctly balanced between each other. Finally, Fig. 16-(g) shows how the i_{circ} is able to follow the dc component given by the control with an associated ripple. Therefore, these figures validate the correct operation of the proposed i_{circ} control.

Fig. 17 compares the i_{circ} provided by the converter when there is not i_{circ} control and when the proposed i_{circ} control is applied. Fig. 17-(a) shows the i_{circ} where the i_{circ} control

VI. CONCLUSION

A novel circulating current control method for MMCs has been presented, which can be employed along with (N+1) SHE-PWM. Through this control, the DC and fundamental components of the circulating current reference are correctly followed, balancing the energy between the phase arms and controlling the SM capacitor averaged voltage. In particular, this technique utilizes two different modulation indexes, m_1 and m_2 , which are applied in the upper or lower arms, generating v_{diff} values which are useful to follow the i_{circ} reference. In addition, due to the utilization of values for $(m_a - m_1)$ and $(m_2 - m_a)$ which remain constant in time, the phase output voltage is not disturbed by the control.

Simulation results have been presented that corroborate the correct operation of the proposed control when 17 firing angles in the first QW are utilized. However, this method requires higher SM capacitance than i_{circ} controls based on high switching frequency modulations, such as PD-PWM.

On the other hand, experimental results have also been obtained demonstrating the ability of the proposed method to control the circulating current and to limit the SM capacitor voltage ripple, without disturbing the phase output voltage.

Regarding the impact on converter efficiency, two main conclusions have been extracted. Firstly, considering the switching losses, (N+1) SHE-PWM is significantly more efficient than PD-PWM, providing similar THD. Secondly, the total losses provided by (N+1) SHE-PWM are significantly lower than the losses provided by PD-PWM.

These results validate the proposed i_{circ} control and the suitability of applying SHE-PWM along with MMCs whose number of SMs at each arm is not high, as those utilized in medium voltage applications. In addition, this method is interesting in medium voltage applications that require higher stored energy than usual, such as inertia emulation.

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Fig. 17. Experimental results. Circulating current comparison. (a) The proposed circulating current control is activated at the instant $t = 0.45$ s. (b) Circulating current when there is not circulating current controller (load change at $t = 0.45$ s). (c) Circulating current when the proposed circulating current controller is activated (load change at $t = 0.45$ s).

Fig. 18. Experimental results for (N+1) SHE-PWM with 17 angles in the first QW, $f = 50$ Hz and $m_a = 0.8$ where the triplen harmonics are eliminated. (a) V_a waveform. (b) V_a spectrum where the first non-eliminated harmonic is the 35th (1750Hz). (c) Output phase current. (d) Upper and lower arm currents.

is activated at $t = 0.45$ s. As it can be noticed, the proposed control reduces the i_{circ} ripple significantly. On the other hand, Figs. 17-(b) and 17-(c) show the i_{circ} under a load step when there is not i_{circ} control and when the proposed control is applied, respectively. As it can be noticed, the proposed i_{circ} control provides lower i_{circ} ripple and lower transition time.

Finally, Fig. 18 provides the experimental results when 17 firing angles are calculated for a single-phase system, whose all harmonics (including the triplen) have been eliminated, providing the first non-eliminated harmonic at 1750Hz (see Fig. 18-(b)). In addition, Fig. 18-(b) shows how the phase neutral voltage spectrum is not disturbed by the application of the proposed i_{circ} control, validating the correct operation of the control when it is applied to a single-phase system, even under the load step depicted in Figs. 18-(c) and 18-(d).

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